

**The Threats to Freedom of Assembly in the Age of AI Development:
Research Insights from Georgia**

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Abstract

This research examines the human rights implications of AI-driven mass surveillance, with a focus on its impact on the right to freedom of assembly. AI technologies such as facial recognition systems and smart surveillance cameras are developing and increasingly deployed in order to ensure public order and security but their use often results in the suppression of civil liberties, particularly in countries with democratic backsliding. Using Georgia as a case study, the research explores how the Georgian government employs AI surveillance tools to monitor, intimidate, and penalize protest participants. Face-to-face, semi-structured in-depth interviews with Georgia lawyers and Georgian protest participants who were fined showed that surveillance technologies are being used not for public safety but as instruments of political repression. The research examines European countries' standards and practices regarding AI-driven mass surveillance in relation to freedom of assembly. It emphasizes that European regulatory frameworks provide important legal standards but they are not sufficient on their own; it is ultimately the political will and quality of democratic governance that determine whether AI surveillance technologies are used to safeguard public interest or to suppress fundamental rights

Introduction

Artificial intelligence is enabling the development of invaluable services and taking part in more and more aspects of our lives. Built from data, hardware and connectivity, AI allows machines to mimic human intelligence such as perception, problem-solving, linguistic interaction or creativity. However, these rapid changes raise major issues.¹ While generative AI models hold tremendous potential for innovation and creativity, they also open the door to misuse in various ways for democratic societies. Since the recent popularization of powerful generative artificial intelligence (AI) systems, there are growing fears that they will impact and destabilize democracies in unforeseen ways,² especially by countries that have a tendency towards authoritarianism. Generative AI threatens three central pillars of democratic governance: representation, accountability, and ultimately, the most important currency in a political system—trust.³

One of the primary dangers of AI in the hands of governments is its interaction with mass surveillance. The term "surveillance" is used in different ways. A literal definition of surveillance as "watching over" indicates monitoring the behavior of persons, objects, or systems. Mass surveillance is also known as "passive" or "undirected" surveillance.⁴ Mass surveillance has been

¹ Gabriela Ramos, Ethics of Artificial Intelligence, [UNESCO](#).

² Raluca Csernaton, Can Democracy Survive the Disruptive Power of AI?, [Carnegie Europe, December 18, 2024](#).

³ Sarah Kreps and Doug Kriner, *How AI Threatens Democracy*, [Journal of Democracy, October 2023](#).

⁴ House of Lords, Surveillance: Citizens and the State - [Constitution Committee Contents](#).

used by countries in various ways. The most common mechanism used has been CCTV cameras. Traditional CCTV systems record events without analyzing the data in real time, often requiring significant human oversight.⁵ Technological progress has reshaped the landscape of mass surveillance. AI has enhanced surveillance cameras by enabling real-time analysis of video streams through advanced algorithms. An example of AI-powered surveillance is facial recognition technologies (FRT). Facial recognition technology (FRT) enables identity validation by measuring and analyzing a person's facial image and comparing it against other samples in a database. Facial recognition systems rely on AI, particularly machine learning and deep learning, to detect, analyze, and match faces. These systems are trained on large datasets to recognize patterns in facial features. This technology is quickly bridging the gap between traditional surveillance.⁶ Along with facial recognition systems, modern surveillance cameras are being developed with advanced zoom capabilities and high-resolution imaging, setting them apart from traditional CCTV cameras. Facial recognition systems can be used for authentication, which means verification of identity and tracking a face on several recorded images. Therefore, since AI-driven surveillance can interpret, predict, and react to situations and handle massive amounts of video data with remarkable accuracy,⁷ it becomes a dangerous surveillance mechanism in the hands of governments.

The rapid proliferation of AI-driven surveillance technologies raises critical concerns about their potential impact on human rights⁸, such as privacy, freedom of expression and freedom of assembly. Digital technologies have significantly expanded the capabilities of authorities to surveil assemblies, including protests. Technologies are used to monitor the planning and organization of protests, to conduct surveillance during protests and even to continue surveillance after protests.⁹ Accordingly, how AI-driven mass surveillance undermine the exercise of freedom of assembly? Despite that, in light of advanced surveillance capabilities, will individuals begin to alter their normal behavior to avoid unwanted inferences¹⁰ - thus resulting in

⁵ IntelliSee, AI Security Cameras vs. Traditional CCTV: [A Head-to-Head Comparison](#).

⁶ Catarina Fontes, Ellen Hohma, Caitlin C. Corrigan, and Christoph Lütge, AI-powered Public Surveillance Systems: Why We (Might) Need Them and How We Want Them, [Technology in Society, November 2022](#).

⁷ Nsoft Vision, Traditional vs. AI Video Surveillance: [A Comparative Insight](#).

⁸ Tulika Singh, AI-Driven Surveillance Technologies and Human Rights: [Balancing Security and Privacy, September 30, 2024](#).

⁹ Iliia Siatitsa, Freedom of Assembly Under Attack: General and Indiscriminate Surveillance and Interference with Internet Communications, [International Review of the Red Cross, 2019](#).

¹⁰ Daragh Murray, Pete Fussey, Kuda Hove, Wairagala Wakabi, Paul Kimumwe, Otto Saki, and Amy Stevans, The Chilling Effects of Surveillance and Human Rights: [Insights from Qualitative Research in Uganda and Zimbabwe, July 31, 2023](#).

a chilling effect from AI-driven mass surveillance? This research aims to answer these questions and explore how AI-driven mass surveillance poses a threat to freedom of assembly and why it creates a chilling effect on freedom of assembly. The research will examine European countries' standards and practices regarding AI-driven mass surveillance, particularly in relation to freedom of assembly, to determine what legal frameworks exist in democratic states and what protection mechanisms are in place to safeguard fundamental human rights. The study examines current practices in Georgia, a country that has increasingly shown authoritarian tendencies in recent years and is actively using AI-powered surveillance to monitor and target protesters. Consequently, the research will enable a comparison between European standards/practices and those of a country shifting toward authoritarianism.

The research is based on a qualitative approach, using face-to-face, semi-structured in-depth interviews with Georgian lawyers and Georgian protest participants who were fined.

Freedom of Assembly

The right to freedom of assembly is codified in Article 21 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights:

The right of peaceful assembly shall be recognized. No restrictions may be placed on the exercise of this right other than those imposed in conformity with the law and which are necessary in a democratic society in the interests of national security or public safety, public order (*ordre public*), the protection of public health or morals or the protection of the rights and freedoms of others.¹¹

The right to peaceful assembly provides an essential means for individuals or groups to express their opinion on matters of public interest and to participate in public life.¹² The protection of the right to peacefully assemble is crucial to creating a tolerant and pluralistic society.

It is explicitly recognized that an assembly may result in disruption to daily life, but this should not justify preventing the assembly, of itself (*Kudrevicius and Others v. Lithuania* [2015](#): 155). Similarly, while assemblies with violent intent are not protected by the right to freedom of assembly, isolated acts of violence do not deprive an assembly as a whole of protection. This is an important element of human rights protection, as isolated acts of violence are frequently used

¹¹ General Assembly, International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, [Resolution 2200A \(XXI\), December 16, 1966](#)

¹² See UN Human Rights Committee General Comment No. 25, *op. cit.*, note 17, para. 8.

as a pretext for broader crackdowns or restrictions.¹³ As stated by the UN Special Rapporteur on the Rights to Freedom of Assembly and Association: The rights to freedom of peaceful assembly and of association play a key role in empowering individuals belonging to groups most at risk to claim other rights and overcome the challenges associated with marginalization. Such rights must therefore not only be protected, but also facilitated.

The inter-relationship between freedom of assembly and other civil and political rights is especially important in relation to protest activities. While the ‘right to protest’ is not *expressly* recognized in either regional or international human rights treaties, the right to peaceful protest is generally protected under international human rights law through a combination of the inter-related rights¹⁴. Freedom of assembly is a fundamental mechanism through which citizens can express their views and protest. While governments may face dissenting opinions that challenge their actions, they are nonetheless obligated to uphold this right. This duty entails both positive obligations, such as facilitating peaceful gatherings, and negative obligations, meaning they must refrain from unjust interference. Consequently, any measures that hinder the exercise of this right undermine the core principles of freedom of assembly.

AI-Driven Mass Surveillance: A Danger to Freedom of Assembly

As AI technology integrates with surveillance, it becomes more desirable to governments. According to the 2019 AI Global Surveillance Index, 56 out of 176 countries now use AI technologies for surveillance purposes.¹⁵ It is important to emphasize that state surveillance is not inherently unlawful but technology has changed the nature of how governments carry out surveillance and what they choose to monitor. Technological progress is a key driver of development and should not be viewed as inherently incompatible with human rights. What

¹³ European Court of Human Rights, *Case of FRUMKIN v. RUSSIA*, (Application no. 74568/12), [January 5, 2016](#).

¹⁴ See, Report of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights, A/HRC/25/32: “Seminar on Effective Measures and Best Practices to Ensure the Promotion and Protection of Human Rights in the Context of Peaceful Protests”, OHCHR, 2 December 2013; Michael O’Flaherty, “Effective measures and best practices to ensure the promotion and protection of human rights in the context of peaceful protests: a background paper”, available at <<http://www.ohchr.org/Documents/Issues/FAssociation/Seminar2013/BackgroundPaperSeminar.doc>>; See also, Wilton Park, Conference Report: ‘Peaceful protest: a cornerstone of democracy. How to address the challenges?’ (26-28 January 2012, WP1154); Article 19, *The Right to Protest: Principles on the protection of human rights in protests* (December 2016), available at: <<https://www.article19.org/resources/the-right-to-protest-principles-on-the-protection-of-human-rights-in-protests/>>. See also, Inter-American Commission on Human Rights, Special Rapporteur for Freedom of Expression, ‘*Protest and Human Rights*’ (Thematic report of the IACHR Special Rapporteur for Freedom of Expression, Edison Lanza, forthcoming 2018).

¹⁵ Steven Feldstein, *The Global Expansion of AI Surveillance*, [Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, September 1, 2019](#).

matters is the strategy, approach, and standards a country adopts in utilizing technological tools. European strategies - outlined below - offer valuable guidance for managing the risks associated with technologies such as surveillance cameras. However, recent data shows a global decline in democratic governance, and in countries shifting toward authoritarianism, the risk of such technologies being used to infringe upon citizens' rights is growing. The research which was conducted by Freedom House in 2022 suggest that a total of 60 countries suffered democratic declines over the past year, while only 25 improved. As of today, some 38 percent of the global population live in not free countries, the highest proportion since 1997. Only about 20 percent now live in free countries¹⁶. Also the research which was made by Democracy Institute (V-Dem) at the University of Gothenburg in 2023 shows that 28 percent of the world's population, 2.2 billion people, now live in closed autocracies compared to 13 percent, 1 billion people, who live in liberal democracies.¹⁷ Recent research which was made by Pew Research Center in February 2024 suggest that the European support for authoritarianism grows - The report found that 60% of respondents in 24 countries worldwide are becoming "increasingly disillusioned with how democracies are managed."¹⁸ Authoritarian governments and the ones who have that kind of tendencies employ various methods to maintain their grip on power and AI can become a powerful tool in their hands to control and suppress citizens. We will see a clear example of this dynamic in the case study of Georgia.

AI-driven mass surveillance provides governments with the ability to identify individuals in real-time, turning these technologies into potential tools of repression. AI systems can analyze protest footage to identify individuals, map social connections. This data can be misused by authorities to intimidate, harass, or blacklist activists and dissidents.¹⁹ In addition protests often rely on collective anonymity for safety and solidarity. AI surveillance systems compromise this by identifying individuals in crowds, deterring people from joining movements they support.

General and indiscriminate surveillance intensifies during protests to ensure that not a single person remains anonymous during a protest. It is now becoming a certainty that protesters could be identified through the data collected by the authorities when it is processed and analyzed. For instance, the regular audio-visual recording of protests in combination with facial recognition technology requires the collection and processing of facial images of all persons captured by the

¹⁶ Sarah Repucci and Amy Slipowitz, The Global Expansion of Authoritarian Rule, [Freedom House, February 2022](#).

¹⁷ Staffan Ingemar Lindberg, The World is Becoming Increasingly Authoritarian – But There Is Hope, [March 2, 2023](#).

¹⁸ Laura Silver and Janell Fetterolf, Who Likes Authoritarianism and How Do They Want to Change Their Government?, [February 28, 2024](#).

¹⁹ D. Murray and P. Fussey, "Bulk Surveillance in the Digital Age: Rethinking the Human Rights Law Approach to Bulk Monitoring of Communications Data," [Israel Law Review 51, no. 1 \(2019\)](#)

camera (irrespective of whether the authorities use facial recognition in real time or at a later stage). The permanent record that can be created by these recordings could allow authorities, if they so decide, to identify all those that participated in a protest even at a later time.²⁰ So AI-enhanced surveillance facilitates the individualization of collective action, a fundamental threat to the right to assemble. Traditionally, public protest offers a degree of anonymity: a person is one face among many. This anonymity is vital - it provides safety, allows people to express unpopular opinions, and reduces fear of retaliation. AI erodes this protection. Facial recognition systems can identify individuals in a crowd, link them to social media profiles²¹, and catalog their political affiliations or protest history.

While citizens should be able to exercise their right to freedom of assembly without fear, restriction, or prohibition, AI-driven mass surveillance poses a significant threat to this fundamental right.

A Chilling Effect on Freedom of Assembly

One of the most insidious ways AI-driven surveillance infringes upon the right to assemble is through its capacity to induce a chilling effect. The "chilling effect" refers to a phenomenon where individuals or groups refrain from engaging in expression for fear of running afoul of a law or regulation.²² The existence of a surveillance-related 'chilling effect' is a well-known phenomenon that arises when individuals or groups modify their behavior due to a fear of the consequences that may result if that behavior is observed.²³

The chilling effect is a relevant issue within the scope of this study, as uncertainty about how surveillance footage is processed, the extent to which it can be used against individuals and in what forms, may discourage participation in protests. Understanding the impact of any potential chilling effect is essential to evaluate the human rights compliance of current surveillance techniques as well as more future-oriented large-scale surveillance and analytical capabilities.

A chilling effect on freedom of assembly is inevitable in circumstances where AI-driven mass surveillance becomes a mechanism of repression. When there is a risk that the exercise of

²⁰Iliia Siatitsa, Freedom of Assembly Under Attack: General and Indiscriminate Surveillance and Interference with Internet Communications, [International Review of the Red Cross, 2019](#).

²¹ Staff Member and Tatum Millet, A Face in the Crowd: Facial Recognition Technology and the Value of Anonymity, [Columbia Journal of Transnational Law, October 18, 2020](#).

²² David L. Hudson Jr., *Chilling Effect Overview*, [Foundation for Individual Rights and Expression](#).

²³ Shane Witnov and Margot E. Kaminski, The Conforming Effect: First Amendment Implications of Surveillance, Beyond Chilling Speech, [University of Richmond Law Review, January 17, 2015](#).

freedom of assembly will lead to identification, which could later become an instrument of intimidation, fines, and possibly arrest by the state, people will refrain from exercising this right.

The extensive capabilities of modern surveillance systems may pressure individuals to modify their behavior, avoiding actions that could attract unwanted scrutiny. As a result, people may distance themselves from lawful yet potentially controversial activities, such as exploring unconventional ideas, engaging with particular social circles, participating in protests, or becoming involved in political movements, out of concern for possible consequences.²⁴ As individuals internalize the risk of being surveilled, they may increasingly engage in self-censorship - not just in protest participation, but in political speech, association, and activism more generally.

The chilling effect operates not only through fear of punishment but also through a gradual erosion of civic trust, discouraging political engagement and reducing the diversity of voices in public discourse.²⁵ By enabling authorities to monitor, track, and identify participants in real time, such surveillance creates a climate of fear that discourages individuals from engaging in protests and public gatherings, ultimately undermining democratic participation.

To avoid the chilling effect, transparent legal regulations are essential. In this regard, it would be interesting to assess European practice, where there are a number of regulations regarding the use of AI surveillance.

European Countries Approach to AI-driven Mass Surveillance: Safeguarding Rights in the Digital Age

Even back in 1978, the European Court of Human Rights ruled in the case of *Klass and Others v. Germany* that “The Court observed in particular that powers of secret surveillance of citizens, characterizing as they do the police state, are tolerable under the Convention only in so far as strictly necessary for safeguarding the democratic institutions.”²⁶ Years later, with the development of technology, the issue has clearly become more problematic. This is why the European Union, the UN, and various European countries have developed a number of standards that provide important safeguards against AI-driven mass surveillance. A striking example is Joint Declaration on Freedom of Peaceful Assembly and of Association and Misuse of Digital

²⁴ Murray et al., [The Chilling Effects of Surveillance and Human Rights](#).

²⁵ J. W. Penney, “Chilling Effects: Online Surveillance and Wikipedia Use,” [Berkeley Technology Law Journal](#), 31, no. 1, 2016.

²⁶ European Court of Human Rights, *Case of Klass and Others v. Germany* (Application no. 5029/71), [September 6, 1978](#).

Technologies, dated 15 September 2023.²⁷ It discusses the importance of freedom of assembly and the obligation of states to ensure its protection and prevent undue interference. Additionally, it outlines several standards for how technological advancements, particularly those used for surveillance, should respect and coexist with the right to freedom of assembly. The following are examples of these standards:

Technologies should be used as a means to facilitate the exercise of the rights to freedom of peaceful assembly, of association and of expression offline and online and not to suppress or unduly restrict these rights.

- States should refrain from and cease the practice of unnecessary and disproportionate surveillance of those exercising their rights to peaceful assembly, of association and expression, in both physical and online spaces.
- To counter AI-based repression, the EU could impose either targeted sanctions against individuals, companies or governments that use AI for repressive purposes, or sectorial sanctions targeting sectors that contribute to the authoritarian use of AI, such as advanced computing, facial recognition technology or surveillance equipment.²⁸ (European Parliament)

In the third edition of the Guidelines on Freedom of Peaceful Assembly (This guideline provide guidance on how states can ensure the right to freedom of peaceful assembly) which were developed by the OSCE office for Democratic Institutions and Human Rights (ODIHR) is also reinforces the right to freedom of assembly in the context of surveillance. Paragraph 172 states that "Overt and covert surveillance of assembly participants should be strictly regulated and should follow a published policy. Digital images of organizers and participants in an assembly should not be recorded, except where specifically authorized by law and necessary in cases where there is probable cause to believe that the planners, organizers or participants will engage in serious unlawful activity. In general, intrusive overt or covert surveillance methods should only be applied where there is clear evidence that imminent unlawful activities, such as violence or use of fire arms are planned to take place during an assembly."²⁹

The UN also developed standards in 2024 regarding how and when surveillance can be used during protests. In this technical and practical toolkit which was developed by the UN Special Rapporteur on the rights to freedom of peaceful assembly and of association is written that facial

²⁷ Joint Declaration on Freedom of Peaceful Assembly and of Association and Misuse of Digital Technologies, [September 15, 2023, pp. 5–9](#).

²⁸ Rasma Kaskina and Angelina Cvetkovska, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Human Rights: Using AI as a Weapon of Repression and Its Impact on Human Rights, [European Parliament, June 2024, pp. 4–5](#).

²⁹ Venice Commission, Guidelines on Freedom of Peaceful Assembly (3rd edition), [July 15, 2020](#).

recognition technologies and other biometric identification technologies must not be utilized to identify or track individuals peacefully participating in a protest. Digital technologies should not be used to categorize, profile or remotely identify individuals, including by biometric means, before, during, or after protests... The use of such technologies at protests is inconsistent with the obligation to facilitate the right to peaceful assembly... Any use of digital technologies should be subject to a rigorous authorization process. The underlying request for authorization should be evidence based and fully justified.³⁰

These developed standards are echoed by the EU AI ACT adopted in 2023, which is a comprehensive regulation aimed at ensuring that artificial intelligence (AI) systems are used safely and ethically within the European Union. The European Union has deemed real-time remote biometric identification systems, such as facial recognition in public spaces, as an unacceptable risk. Under the EU AI Act real-time remote biometric identification systems, such as facial recognition in public spaces are generally banned, with specific exceptions for law enforcement³¹. These exceptions allow such technology only in cases related to serious threats, terrorism prevention, or locating criminal suspects, and they require prior judicial authorization in most cases.

Despite all of this standards and regulations, there are some concerns about how European countries use AI-driven mass surveillance against protestors. Amnesty International in 2024 conducted a research in which serious dangers were revealed. Research suggest that among EU countries, police in Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands and Slovenia already employ facial recognition technology (FRT) and countries including Czechia, Portugal, Spain are among those which are expected to follow the trend. There has also been a recent and marked increase in the use of facial recognition technology by law enforcement in the UK, including at protests. In 2019, UN Special Rapporteur on extreme poverty and human rights expressed concerns towards the Netherlands in relation to “increasing degree of police surveillance... during peaceful assemblies, which reportedly have a chilling effect on demonstrations”. The same concerns were raised in 2021 about UK where there is “increased use by police forces of facial recognition technology to monitor peaceful gatherings”. In Greece, under the current legislation, surveillance systems can be installed and operated during demonstrations. France in May 2023 for the 2024 Olympic and Paralympic games legalized the pervasive use of video surveillance powered by artificial intelligence.³² The UN

³⁰ OHCHR, [Toolkit on Law Enforcement and Digital Technologies, 2024](#).

³¹ European Parliament, EU AI Act: First Regulation on Artificial Intelligence, [February 19, 2025](#).

³² 32 Europe: Under Protected and Over Restricted: The State of the Right to Protest in 21 European Countries, Amnesty International, [July 8, 2024](#).

Human Rights Committee recently expressed concerns about the use of surveillance technology in the UK. They were concerned about the increased use by police forces of facial recognition technology to monitor peaceful gatherings.³³ The police in Hamburg used facial recognition software Videmo 360 during the protests against the G20 summit in 2017. The database includes 100.000 individuals in Hamburg during the G20 summit and whose profiles are saved in the police database. The technology allows for the determination of behavior, participation in gatherings, preferences, and religious or political engagement.³⁴ In March 2025, Hungary, three amendments aimed to criminalize LGBTQAI+ demonstrations and increase biometric surveillance were rushed through the Hungarian Parliament within 24 hours and without any public debate. These amendments, which entered into force on 15 April, dramatically expand the use of facial recognition technology (FRT) in Hungary, including in the context of minor infractions and peaceful assemblies, such as Budapest Pride. The Civil Liberties Union for Europe, EDRi, the European Center for Not-for-Profit Law, and the Hungarian Civil Liberties Union argue that using FRT to identify attendees of banned Pride events or minor offenses breaches the EU AI Act and the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.³⁵

Existing practices pose certain risks in the use of facial recognition technology but such cases cannot be considered alarming. Of particular importance is the processing of information obtained from cameras - whether they will be used against citizens, to intimidate them, and with the aim of restricting citizens' freedom of assembly or creating a chilling effect. Based on existing practices, there is no sufficient evidence to conclude that such misuse is taking place. In contrast, such a threat is present in Georgia - a country that, in recent years, has shown a clear trend toward authoritarianism. While European countries, despite some unfavorable practices, have implemented various safeguards regarding the use of advanced technological tools, Georgia currently lacks any comparable mechanisms. On the contrary, these technologies have increasingly been used as instruments of intimidation and to restrict the freedom of assembly.

AI-Driven Mass Surveillance and Freedom of Assembly in Georgia: A Political Context

The Georgian government, which is struggling with legitimacy both domestically and internationally, is actively using facial recognition technology to intimidate protesters. Before examining this issue in detail, it is crucial to understand the broader political context.

³³ Nicola Newson, UN Standards on the Use of Surveillance Technology at Protests, UK Parliament, [April 18, 2024](#).

³⁴ Francesco Ragazzi, Elif Mendos Kuskonmaz, Ildikó Plájás, Ruben van de Ven, and Ben Wagner, *Biometric and Behavioural Mass Surveillance in EU Member States*, [Report for the Greens/EFA in the European Parliament](#).

³⁵ European Center for Not-for-Profit Law, Hungary's New Biometric Surveillance Laws Violate the AI Act, [April 28, 2025](#).

The Georgian government has been openly displayed authoritarian tendencies in recent years. There are many concerns about the country's progress towards democracy and the rule of law. Problems are highlighted by a political crisis, which escalated in November 2020 after opposition politicians claimed that the ruling Georgian Dream party had rigged parliamentary elections, and decided to boycott the parliament.³⁶ Survey conducted in March 2022 found that 41 percent of Georgians felt that democracy had regressed over the past year. The country's ruling party, Georgian Dream, has been accused of expanding control over state institutions and security forces, infringing on civil society work and independent media, committing election malpractice.³⁷ The next parliamentary elections which was held in 2024 signal the country's descent into hegemonic authoritarianism. The ruling Georgian Dream party won by engaging in election manipulation, adopting the classical illiberal-authoritarian playbook, spreading disinformation about simultaneously remaining on the EU enlargement track and instrumentalizing Russia's threat to the country.³⁸ This parliamentary election marked another milestone in the dramatic deterioration of the relationship between the government and the EU that resulted in the de facto halting of the accession process in June. In the election, the Georgian Dream (GD), a party founded and dominated by the billionaire Bidzina Ivanishvili, claimed a fourth consecutive victory.³⁹ The opposition claims that the GD orchestrated widespread fraud and stole the election. As a result, they have refused to take up their seats in the new parliament, calling for an international inquiry while organizing protests at home⁴⁰.

Soon after the election tens of thousands of pro-Europe protesters rallied outside Georgia's parliament building in the capital Tbilisi. Anti-government protests erupted after the ruling Georgian Dream party announced a suspension in the country's EU-bid. Georgia has been gripped by a wave of unprecedented turmoil after incumbent Prime Minister Irakli Kobakhidze announced a four-year suspension in EU accession talks on 28 November. The move triggered daily mass protests which often turned violent, with police forces using riot teams, tear gas and

³⁶ Martin Russell, Georgia's Bumpy Road to Democracy, [European Parliament, May 2021](#).

³⁷ Caroline Kapp and Liana Fix, The Dangers of Democratic Backsliding in Georgia, Council on Foreign Relations, [June 21, 2023](#).

³⁸ Sonja Schiffers, The 2024 Elections in Georgia: Descent into Hegemonic Authoritarianism, Heinrich Böll Stiftung Brussels (European Union), [October 29, 2024](#).

³⁹ Ondrej Ditrych, Trouble in Tbilisi: How the EU Should Respond to Georgia's Drift Towards Authoritarianism, European Union Institute for Security Studies, [November 27, 2024](#).

⁴⁰ ENEMO, Statement of Preliminary Findings and Conclusions, [October 27, 2024](#).

water cannons routinely to disperse demonstrators.⁴¹ According to Transparency International Georgia, from November 28 to December 6, more than 400 people were arrested – more than 350 people on administrative charges and 26 people on criminal charges. Of these, more than 300 reported being physically assaulted and/or tortured. More than 80 detainees have been hospitalized. Of the detainees, 7 are foreigners. Punished policemen – 0. As of the latest count, there are more than 50 political prisoners in Georgia during these protests.

Shortly after the protests commenced, the Georgian Dream-led single-party parliament enacted a package of repressive laws. These measures imposed a series of authoritarian restrictions on freedom of expression and assembly, established a mechanism for preventive detention, and significantly increased fines for violations. The persecution of hundreds of individuals remains ongoing, with authorities retroactively identifying and penalizing participants for their presence at the demonstrations. The Ministry of Internal Affairs classifies mere attendance at a protest as an unlawful road obstruction, imposing fines of no less than 5,000 GEL (about USD 1800) on alleged violators.⁴² The increase in the fine was particularly useful, as it had become a mechanism of intimidation. From November 28, 2024 to March 18, 2025, fines imposed on protesters accused by authorities of blocking roads reached GEL 2 million (about USD 715,000), according to GYLA. Surveillance cameras made it possible to identify and fine those participating in the protest. On February 6, RFE/RL’s Tbilisi bureau published a detailed report on the rapid expansion of surveillance cameras across Georgia and the lack of public awareness regarding their management and capabilities. The growing network of surveillance cameras has heightened concerns, as it coincides with an increasingly authoritarian trend in the country, the brutal repression of protests and dissent, and the shrinking of civil liberties in Georgia. The number of cameras has reportedly increased exponentially, particularly at the sites of the ongoing popular protests. In recent days, many of the protesters have been summoned by the public prosecutor’s office in connection with alleged road blockades in December and January. According to the investigation, most of the cameras are made by two Chinese companies: *Hikvision* and *Dahua Technology*. Both companies are sanctioned by the United States. Denmark, the United Kingdom, and Australia have refused to use their equipment.⁴³ The Innovations and Reforms Center estimates that there are at least 4,318 “smart cameras” installed across Georgia,⁴⁴ which implies mass surveillance control.

⁴¹ Malek Fouda, Tens of Thousands Take to the Streets of Tbilisi in Anti-Government Protests on New Year's Eve, [January 1, 2025](#).

⁴² Georgian Democracy Initiative, Political Prisoners of the Regime in Georgia, [February 2, 2025](#).

⁴³ Civil Georgia, RFE/RL’s Investigation Explores Concerns Over Georgia’s Expanding Surveillance System, [February 8, 2025](#).

⁴⁴ Innovations and Reforms Centre, [Monitoring Personal Data Protection in Smart Camera Systems, 2020](#).

Interior Ministry's continued use of facial recognition cameras against protesters in courts, particularly in the cases involving roadblocks, raises "serious privacy and legal concerns", the Georgian Young Lawyers' Association said. The GYLA notes that surveillance cameras are often the only evidence used in such cases, with courts accepting images from the cameras as sufficient proof of guilt. However, the watchdog adds, the courts typically overlook critical legal questions, such as whether the individuals were identified properly or if the person responsible for the identification had the necessary access to protected databases as required by personal data protection laws. This approach is seen as a tactic to intimidate and control protesters. GYLA further reports a recent case, which it says has brought to light the Ministry's use of targeted surveillance. GYLA says it discovered that, in a video submitted as evidence from a January 2025 protest on Rustaveli Avenue, the Ministry had actively tracked an individual during the protest. The footage shows a camera following the protester in real-time, zooming in on a document the person was reading. GYLA says this reveals a clear instance of targeted surveillance, suggesting that a specific person or group of people are manually controlling the cameras.⁴⁵ The strengthening of mass surveillance mechanisms led to a decrease in the number of participants in the protest over time.

Research Insights from Georgia

Vague and unconstitutional legal regulations

Lawyers

- The study found that Georgia's legislative framework regarding facial recognition cameras fails to provide an effective balance between security and human rights. Although there is law of Georgia on personal data protection, which establishes the grounds and principles for data processing, there is a vague provision in the case of biometric data processing. The aforementioned norm provides for general grounds, including the protection of public security, which in turn is a broad term and requires a correct interpretation in practice. A key development occurred with the December 2024 legislative amendment, which significantly lowered the threshold for processing sensitive data. Under the revised law, the detection of administrative offenses - including photographing individuals and processing data related to facial recognition - is now explicitly permitted without requiring the court to justify its connection to public security. This legislative change undermines the principles of data

⁴⁵ Georgian Young Lawyers' Association, The Ministry of Internal Affairs Uses Facial Recognition Technology for Total Control Against Peaceful Protesters, [March 12, 2025](#).

protection as defined by both national and international standards, particularly in terms of proportionality and data minimization.

As one lawyer highlighted during an interview:

“Blocking the road does not pose such a threat to public safety that it would justify mass control. In addition, the installed cameras record not only the roadway, but also the sidewalk, and not only the course of the protest, but also in a continuous mode and record the movement of people throughout the day. This is functionally equivalent to mass control, is not justified in this context, and contradicts both national legislation and international standards in terms of proportionality and purpose limitation.”

The Court’s Formal Approach to Evidence Evaluation

Lawyers

- Interviews have revealed that the court does not verify the legitimacy of evidence obtained from surveillance cameras and identifies protest participants as administrative violators based solely on these recordings.
- The court only considers records requested from 112 (Public Safety Management Center) in cases related to roadblocks. The court has not assessed in any case so far how lawful the processing of data is and whether such material can be used as evidence. That is why lawyers do not even raise this request, because, as one of the respondents noted in an interview: **“The court will approach the process of examining evidence absolutely formally. There is no reasonable expectation that the court will not use this evidence.”**
- Protesters are not allowed to question witnesses in the case. The court relies solely on camera footage, even though police often order street closures before citizens occupy the area.

Nontransparent procedures

Lawyers

- It is unclear how information from cameras is processed by AI-powered facial recognition systems, and what databases these facial recognition systems have access to.
- The Ministry of Internal Affairs of Georgia has not disclosed the technical specifications of the surveillance cameras used, nor has it provided information about who has access to the

recordings, how long the data is stored, or whether any safeguards exist to limit unauthorized access.

- The Personal Data Protection Service, which is obliged to assess whether data is being processed lawfully, has not published a decision or opinion on the use of surveillance cameras. Although it launched a study on its own initiative in February to examine whether the use of facial recognition systems during the protests is legal, there is no interim conclusion yet. The absence of transparency and accountability creates significant risk of misuse:

“Unpredictable and opaque procedures open the door for facial recognition systems to be used arbitrarily or for politically motivated purposes”.

Protesters who were fined

The protesters who were fined note that when the state purchased new smart cameras and facial recognition systems, they were unaware of how the system would work, as well as how the information received would be processed. No state agency has made any public information about this available. As the respondents note, the purpose of this was to create an effect of surprise, which took on a special form in February and resulted in numerous citizens being fined on a daily basis. As one of the protesters said:

“After the active deployment of cameras in the protest area, I decided to at least cover my face a little - for this, I would cover it with a cap - but this was not enough, because if you show your face even a little, as I learned after the fine, the new cameras capture facial details in high quality, and subsequently, the facial recognition technology could easily find you in the database.”

AI Surveillance as a Tool of Repression

Respondents note that the use of facial recognition systems and smart cameras against protesters has become a common practice in Georgia.

Lawyers

- During the protests in November and December 2024, when violence against protesters by law enforcement officials was actively taking place, there was an interest in having high-definition cameras on the territory of the protest. Nevertheless, not only was video monitoring installed and strengthened at that time, but the general-view cameras installed in gathering places, as the investigative bodies note, were disconnected and had a technical fault. That is why no law enforcement officer who used violence against protesters has been punished to this day. This raises reasonable suspicions that the state is trying to use the developed technological means against protesters, therefore, its goal is not to prevent crime, but to punish and intimidate citizens.
- Respondents associate the use of camera recordings during the trial with the goal of repression and intimidation of people. As one of the lawyers noted in an interview: **“The state could have used false witnesses, especially when the court is not independent, but the goal of using camera recordings is to send the message that we are watching all of you who participate in demonstrations, we know who you are. Accordingly, 5,000 GEL is only a visible form of this repression, although it is accompanied by other elements such as intimidation and etc. Accordingly, the main goal is to create a total sense of control in society, and to tell and show those who participate in the demonstration that we know who you are and we will definitely come to you.”**
- The state perceives peaceful protests as a form of criminal activity, which is why it seeks to control them and reduce participation. To achieve this objective, it employs advanced technological tools

Protesters who were fined

Protest participants emphasize that the primary aim of the state’s actions is to control and intimidate those involved in demonstrations. On one hand, the imposition of fines functions as a form of financial pressure - referred to by some as *financial terrorism* - intended to discourage participation by increasing the personal cost of protesting. On the other hand, it also serves as a source of revenue for the state.

Moreover, several respondents reported that following the intensified use of surveillance cameras, they began to experience fear in their daily lives. They expressed concerns that they could be identified even in private settings, such as near their homes, and subsequently subjected to further intimidation. This atmosphere of fear, they suggest, extends beyond protest days and contributes to a broader strategy of repression.

“Since the protests began, I have felt fear in my daily life. When I leave the house, I look back or, if I’m afraid of that, I take out my phone and turn on the front camera to see if anyone is following me.”

- With daily surveillance, participants in the protest feel that the information obtained from surveillance cameras, which are used in conjunction with facial recognition systems, can be used to intimidate them. This includes cases where a police car was parked next to the protesters for several nights, which made them feel afraid and insecure.
- Several respondents noted that although they do not express their position on social networks and do not advertise that they often participate in protests, relatives have called them and told them to stop participating in the protest; otherwise, there would be problems. Obviously, this raises suspicions that they have been subjected to mass surveillance.
- Mass surveillance mechanisms have become especially dangerous for civil servants. As one civil servant noted in an interview:

“After November, I went to protests as often as possible. I always tried to cover my face, so that I wouldn’t meet people I knew and wouldn’t have problems at work. After the cameras were actively installed in protest areas, I reduced my attendance at protests. At least once, a surveillance camera was able to identify me, and I was fined. Soon after, I was told at work to stop going to protests - otherwise, if I was caught again, I would be fired.”

Chilling effect

Respondents emphasize that the use of AI-driven mass surveillance technologies, particularly facial recognition, has a pronounced chilling effect on the exercise of freedom of assembly. Many citizens report opting out of protests entirely, fearing that their identities could be captured and linked to their actions, leading to legal consequences.

Lawyers

- the Ministry of Internal Affairs is capable of initiating legal proceedings against hundreds of individuals in a single night, based on footage collected by smart surveillance cameras deployed during demonstrations. This capacity to process and prosecute at scale, made possible by AI, acts as a powerful deterrent.
- Moreover, the lack of legal clarity exacerbates the chilling effect. Protesters are often uncertain about what exactly constitutes a punishable offense. For example, Can standing on

a blocked street result in a fine? Is standing on the sidewalk or pedestrian areas also punishable? What are the specific legal grounds for such penalties? This ambiguity contributes to a general sense of legal insecurity, discouraging participation and reinforcing the chilling effect.

Protesters who were fined

- Those who still choose to participate in protests report changing their behavior in response to surveillance threats. They covering faces with masks to avoid identification via facial recognition.
- Avoiding areas with visible camera presence or maintaining a lower profile during demonstrations.
- Self-censorship in slogans, posters, or speech, to minimize risk of attracting targeted attention.
- The threat of disproportionate punishment - such as heavy fines further dissuades potential protesters. Even minor acts, if caught on smart surveillance systems, can lead to outcomes that feel excessive or unjust, reinforcing the perception that the system is being used as a tool of intimidation.

Conclusion

The study reveals that AI-driven mass surveillance has become a key mechanism for restricting freedom of assembly. In Georgia, the government employs advanced technological tools not merely for public safety, but as a means of repression and intimidation, aiming to deter citizens from exercising their right to peaceful protest. Importantly, the root of this issue does not lie in the existence of such technologies themselves, but rather in the lack of adequate legal safeguards and regulatory frameworks to govern their use.

At the same time, European experience demonstrates that the mere presence of legal standards is insufficient. What ultimately shapes the deployment of surveillance technologies is the overall policy direction and strategic intent of the state. In countries where the rule of law and democratic values are prioritized, advanced surveillance tools are more likely to be used proportionally and with oversight. Conversely, in environments lacking transparency and accountability, these same tools can easily become instruments of oppression which will cause a chilling effect on freedom of assembly.

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